

EMPLOYEE HEALTH AND SAFETY PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT COUNCILS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: Workplace hazards, poor employee health, mechanical hardware injuries, and disabilities reduces the worker productivity and work/product quality and increase cost. The study examined the Employee health and safety performance of Local Government Councils in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study were to; examine the relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes and evaluate the relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities. The population of the study was One thousand and three hundred and six (13066) staff of the Local Government areas under study. In calculating the sample size of two hundred and ninety seven (297), using Freud and Williams (as quoted by Uzoagulu 2011) at 5 percent error margin. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and interviews. A total of two hundred and ninety seven (297) copies of questionnaire were distributed while two hundred and ten (210) copies of questionnaire were returned and seventy one (71) copies were not returned. Pearson correlation coefficient(r), was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings indicated that there was significant positive relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State, ($r=0.686 < 0.862$, $p < 0.05$) and there was significant positive relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State, ($r=0.638 < 0.835$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that Worker Competency and training, Hazard identification and risk assessment had significant positive relationship with Collection of various rates and taxes, Provisions of health facilities of the Local Government Council Areas of Enugu state, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that there should be effective Worker Competency and training to engage the workers in planning process to communities in the local government and encourages the people to participate in hazard identification processes.

Keywords: Employee, Health and safety, performance, Planning, Community inspection.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Health is increasingly being recognized across the world as a key aspect of development and economic wellbeing of individuals and nations (Piabuo and Tieguhong, 2017). Indeed, there is widespread consensus in academic and policy circles that apart from being a human right, health leads to significant economic gains. Health is both a cause and a consequence of improved performance. However, no occupation or organization is without their own health hazards or accidents. There are always risks associated with doing business, both in the public sector and in the private sector as well. These highlight the need for occupational health and safety management. Furthermore, improving employee productivity and employee health and safety have been an important field of interest of industry especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Some common characteristics of such industries include inappropriate workplace design, ill-structured jobs, mismatch between job demands and worker's abilities, adverse environments, poor human-machine system design, and inappropriate management programs. These factors lead to workplace hazards, poor employee health, mechanical hardware injuries, and disabilities, which reduce the worker productivity and work/product quality and increase the cost (Kaynak, Toklu, Elci and Toklu, 2016).

There is need for adequate safety in the workplace. Work safety includes protecting employees from work accidents. Work safety is a safe or safe condition from work damage or loss. Occupational safety risks are aspects of the work environment that can cause fire, electric current fears, cuts, bruises, sprains, broken bones etc. Safety was explained as the protection from danger and hazards arising out of, linked with or occurring in the course of employment (CSSE, 2015). A safe work environment makes workers healthy and productive. If the company can reduce the level and severity of work accidents, illness and matters related to stress, as well as improve the quality of worklife of its work, the company will be more effective (Kaynak, Toklu, Elci and Toklu, 2016). Improvements in this case will result in improved performance due to decreasing the number of workdays lost. Increased efficiency and quality of workers who are more committed (Yulihardi & Iskamoto, 2018). Cashmere (2016) argues that performance is the results of work and work behavior. If seen based on the results, the focus is the amount of quality and quantity produced by a person. Organizational performance is the comparison of an organization's goals and objectives with its actual performance in three distinct areas – financial performance, market performance, and shareholder value (Ali and Qun, 2019). In order to improve performance, organizations need to understand the importance of employee health and safety, which is the key objective of the current study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is no secret that the health of an individual improves their ability to maximize their own productivity. Therefore, in order to achieve this objective, a conscious effort needs to be made to ensure that those employees are in peak health condition, and that they also feel safe in the organization.

The absence of safety planning in organizations increases the possibility of poor service quality among organizations. Then again, employee safety inspections are carried out to ensure the presence of adequate facilities in the local government councils. Poor community inspections or the absence of it will negatively impact on the employee productivity. Lack of Worker Competency and training Also, incident reporting and a lack of it would always diminish the security chances of Local Government Council Areas in Enugu State.

Poor safety planning, lack of, or poor community inspection and the absence of incident reporting in organizations highly jeopardize the employee health and safety of the workers in these organizations within the local governments. And this will definitely impact on their performance levels negatively. This is the reason why the study examines employee health and safety and performance of local government council areas in Enugu State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the Employee health and safety services and performance of Local Government Councils in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in the Local Government Councils in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities of Local Government Councils in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes of Local Government Council Areas in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities of Local Government Council Areas in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study;

- i. There is no positive significant relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes of Local Government Council Areas in Enugu State.
- ii. There is no positive significant relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in the Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study will be of huge significance to management of various Local Government Areas in Enugu State. The study will be of benefits to the various Local Government Chairmen in the state on the possible ways of improving the overall health of employees under their direct care and leadership. The study will also help the government in identifying the various ways it could improve the safety of its citizens, as well as workers working in the government, while maximizing their output and performance in their various productive roles.

1.7 Scope of the study

The scope of the study was on Employee Health and Safety Services and Performance of Local Government Councils of Enugu State. A Study of Enugu East Senatorial District in Enugu State of Nigeria which covers six local government areas of Enugu East, Enugu North, Enugu South, Isi Uzo, Nkanu East and Nkanu West. The issues were: Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes; employee Hazard identification and risk management and Provisions of health facilities, of the Local Government of Enugu State. Time scope: 2020 – 2022.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Employee

An employee is someone who gets paid to work for a person or company. Workers don't need to work full time to be considered employees – they simply need to be paid to work by an employer (the person or business that pays them). An employee is a term for workers and managers working for a company, organization or community (Muhl, 2020). In the United States, a worker is an employee if their employer gets to tell them what to do, how to do it, and when to do it in a material way and an independent contractor if they get to make their own decisions about how to do what the employer wants (United States Department of Labour, 2020).

2.1.2 Health

Employee health is a term used to describe the overall health of an organization's employees. It encompasses all aspects and dimensions of health and wellness, including physical and mental health. Employee health or employee well-being is one of the most critical aspects of an organization. Healthy employees are widely considered as the pillars of organizational success. (WHO, 2022).

2.1.3 Safety

Safety is frequently defined as the inverse of risk; the lower the risk, the higher the safety. Safety as the antonym of risk certainly captures the important dimensions of safety, but it does not provide an exhaustive understanding of the concept. Business needs to transition from seeing safety as an absence of negatives, such as no serious incidents, to seeing it as the presence of a positive capacity to make work proceed properly. A focus on safety and risk should become a focus of resilience (Dekker, 2015). The fact that incidents are relatively rare events should remind all stakeholders that the absence of a negative does not always result in a strong positive (Smith, 2014).

2.1.4 Service

A service is an (intangible) act or use for which a consumer, firm, or government is willing to pay. Examples include work done by barbers, doctors, lawyers, mechanics, banks, insurance companies, and so on. Public services are those that society (nation state, fiscal union or region) as a whole pays for. Using resources, skill, ingenuity, and experience, service providers benefit service consumers. (McConnell and Campbell, 2009).

2.1.5 Employee Health and Safety Services

Employee safety and health are conditions and factors that or will affect worker Safety and Health (including contract employees and contractors, visitors, and other people at workplace). Robert and Jackson (2009) point out that occupational safety is a condition where the physical well-being of employees is protected while work health is a general condition of the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of the employees where they work. Safety planning refers to all the procedures carried out to ensure that safety as an organizational objective is achieved. When an organization strategically perpetrates its actions to actualize the safety of its employees, then it is safety planning.

2.1.6 Components of Employee Health and Safety Services

These following elements are components of an effective OHS management system: The scope and complexity of the system may vary, depending on the size and hazards of your workplace and the nature of the work performed (Bill, 2021). The components were: Management Leadership and Commitment, Safe Work Procedures and Written Instructions, Health and Safety Training and Instruction, Identifying Hazards and Managing Risk, Inspection of Premises, Equipment, Workplaces & Work practices, Investigation of Incidents, Program Administration, Joint Health and Safety Committee & Representatives, Worker Competency and Training Programmes, Occupational Health and Safety Programs, and System audit, Safety Planning, incident reporting, User-friendly, training, Risk assessments, certification, convenience, performance (Sundberg, 2018 & Rainn, 2021).

2.1.6.1 Worker Competency and training

Training boosts a feeling of value in employees. It shows that the organization is committed to providing them with the resources needed to ensure they are doing a good job. In turn, they are more likely to enjoy their work and remain in the organization for long (O'Neill, 2020).

Training can only be executed when it has been determined which employees should receive training and what their current levels, knowledge and skills are. Consequently, the assessment of the individual will indicate the range of skills and knowledge that is to be attained. Note that the difference between actual performance and required performance will ultimately form the training gap, and therefore indicate the extent of training needed. Training refers to linking the gap between the present performance and the standard desired performance. Training could be given via different methods such as on the coaching and mentoring, peer's cooperation and participation by the subordinates (Cross, 2018). Training refers to the acquisition of skills, knowledge and information directly required for the performance of a specific role. It includes on-the-job training, workshops, seminars and conference. Development broadly refers to job enrichment that has an intrinsic mechanism to motivate an employee to accept and play challenging organizational tasks (Chukwunye and Igbokwe, 2011).

2.1.6.2 Hazard identification and risk assessment

Hazards should be identified before performing a task, as well. This might include double-checking that equipment is functioning properly and that a worker's surroundings are secure. While tasks are being performed, employees should be conscious of any changes in their environment and if an incident occurs, it is important to identify the hazards that were responsible. Even in the event of a 'near miss', it's important to recognize what could have caused an accident in order to prevent that situation from happening in the future. Hazards come in many shapes, some more serious than others, and will vary depending on the working environment (Aaron, 2018). In the financial world, risk management is the process of identification, analysis, and acceptance or mitigation of uncertainty in investment decisions. (Brock, 2021).

2.1.7 Performance

Performance is the results of work and work behavior. If seen based on the results, the focus is the amount of quality and quantity produced by a person. If seen based on work behavior, what is assessed is the behavior of employees in carrying out their obligations that contribute to either positive or negative attitudes towards the fulfillment of company goals. Organizational performance is the comparison of an organization's goals and objectives with its actual performance in three distinct areas financial performance, market performance, and shareholder value, (Cashmere, 2016).

2.1.8 Measurement of Local government councils Performance

Edeh (2021) noted the following as Functions of the Local government: Control and provision of Markets and motor packs, Collection and disposition of refuse, Making recommendations, Provision and control of cemeteries and slaughter houses, Regulation and issuing of birth, death and marriage certificates, They issue and regulate various types of licenses, Naming of streets, Collection of various rates and taxes, Building and maintaining of schools and colleges, Awarding of bursaries and scholarships, Control of public housing, town and housing planning, Provisions of health facilities, Provisions of public libraries, Provisions of pipe borne water and other public institutions. Jesse,(2022), enumerated 143 Local Government KPIs & Scorecard Measures which include: Total Number of Inspections Performed, Total Permit Revenue and Percentage of Historic Preservation Cost Funded by Municipality Funds.

2.1.8.1 Collection of various rates and taxes

Revenue generation implies the amount of money that enters the treasury of the Local Government from time to time. No doubt, revenue generation in Nigeria local governments is principally derived from tax. Tax is a compulsory levy imposed by the government on individuals and companies for the various legitimate function of the state (Olaoye, 2008). Tax is a necessary ingredient for civilization. Recently, the revenue accruing to local government is derived from two broad sources, viz the external sources and the internal source (Olasunkanmi, Banna, Kazeem and Bukola, 2019). Indeed one of the fundamental responsibilities of any Government is to mobilize enough resources to enable to provide necessary services and secure its people.

2.1.8.2 Provisions of health facilities

Government is the bedrock of sustainable human development. This is because government emerged from the exigencies of needs. One of the social challenges of the ordinary people in Nigeria is primary healthcare. Comprehensive health care system based on primary health care that is promotive, protective, preventive, restorative and rehabilitative to all citizens within the available resources to those individuals and communities are assured of productivity, social-well-being and enjoyment of living (Uzochukwu, Onwujekwe and Nkoli, 2014). Health care is a vital in any community. Any health centre with a well implemented PHC program can stand the test of time in curbing less than five mortality and morbidity (Chinawa and Awoere, 2015). There is an immediate need to improve and provide quality health care among children in rural areas and suburban. This is necessary so as to avert the number of death that comes from that part of the country. Various health programs have been instituted in Enugu state aimed at providing and carrying out health care services in remote communities in Enugu and states where PHC operates (Chinawa and Awoere, 2015).

2.1.9 Conceptual Framework of the study

Fig. 2.1. Researchers Models, 2022

The diagram above shows the conceptual linkages between the various components and variables in the study. The diagram shows how the imposition of Worker Competency and training on the Collection of various rates and taxes and also, Hazard identification and risk assessment on the Provisions of health facilities in the Local Governments Councils of Enugu state.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The following theories were reviewed in line with the theories of the study.

Loss Control Theory (Frank Bird (1970) and Behavioral Operant Conditioning Theory (Edward L. Thorndike (1874–1949). The study was anchored on the Loss Control Theory, which tries to explain the need for organization to effectively manage the occurrence of accidents in the organizations. The theories are;

2.2.1 Behavioral Operant Conditioning Theory

This theory was an attempt to explain factors for some employees within the organization to either adopt or reject health and safety programmes for the betterment of themselves and the organization in general. Behavioral safety is the way in which an individual responds to a decision involving risk or safety. Modifying individual behavior can play a very significant role in providing safer workplace and promote organizational performance. Environmental changes often rely on workers behavior. For instances, protective clothing does not protect when it remains on the rack; ventilation systems do not work unless activated; alarms that have been disconnected to eliminate their annoying noise fail to alert workers of dangers (Thorndike, 1920). The theory explains the intricacies involved in instilling new safety culture in a workplace to maximize employee and general performance.

2.2.2 Frank Bird's Loss Control Theory

Frank Bird (1970) developed Loss Control Theory. The accident triangle, also known as Heinrich's triangle or Bird's triangle, is a theory of industrial accident prevention. It shows a relationship between serious accidents, minor accidents and near misses and proposes that if the number of minor accidents is reduced then there will be

a corresponding fall in the number of serious accidents. The triangle was first proposed by Herbert William Heinrich in 1931 and has since been updated and expanded upon by other writers, notably Frank E. Bird. It is often shown pictorially as a triangle or pyramid and has been described as a cornerstone of 20th century workplace health and safety philosophy. In recent times it has come under criticism over the values allocated to each category of accident and for focusing only on the reduction in minor injuries (Andersen and Denkl, 2010). This theory is vital to the current study since it enumerates the various accidents that could take place in the work, as well as ways to reduce the effect of minor injuries in the working space.

2.3 Empirical Review

The empirical review of the study was based on the objectives of the study

2.3.1 Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes

Kaynack, Toklu, Elci and Toklu (2016) investigated occupational health and safety (OHS) practices in five dimensions, i.e. safety procedures and risk management, safety and health rules, first aid support and training, occupational accident prevention, and organizational safety support. A survey form was developed in order to investigate the effect of OHS practices on work alienation, organizational commitment, and job performance as a throughput of such practices. The data set obtained from private sector enterprises was analyzed by structural equation modeling using least squares method. The findings of the analysis suggested that such OHS practices as safety procedures and risk management, safety and health rules, first aid support and training, and organizational safety support had a positive effect on organizational commitment.

Wahlin, Kvarnstrom, Nisling and Ohrn (2019) examined learning from incident reporting systems and how they affect the culture of safety for healthcare workers and patients. The aim of the retrospective study was to explore patient injuries focusing on falls. Furthermore, on healthcare workers' incidents, injuries and the situations they occurred. A total of 65,749 patient risks and incidents were registered in the incident reporting system between 2011 and 2014. Of these, 11,006 were classified as an injury to a patient. Risks and incidents were registered and analyzed for 1702 healthcare workers. The results of the study show that fifteen percent of the patient injuries required treatment. Falls were reported in 17% of the cases. Patients fell mainly in unassisted situations.

Mujino (2019) analyzed the effect of occupational safety and health (X1), organizational culture (X2), communication (Y1) as the mediating variable on the organizational performance (Y2) the research method was a quantitative approach. The research population was 150 employees at PT. PEM. Questionnaires that were distributed to the respondents used Likert Scale with 5 levels of answers. The data collection techniques employed was interview and questionnaire. The questionnaire survey sheets were sent randomly to the employees of PT. PEM. Then the data were analyzed using Smart PLS (Partial Least Square). The results of this research are as follows. The occupational safety and health variable had a positive and significant effect on the communication variable, the occupational safety and health variable had a positive and significant effect on the organizational performance variable.

Moha and Suharyanto (2020) examined the effect of work safety and work healthy on employee productivity in the production department at PT. Sisirau Aceh Tamiang. This research is a type of quantitative research with a sample of 45 people. The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. Hypothesis testing is

done through t test, F test, and the coefficient of determination (R²). Regression equation results obtained $Y = 2.255 + 0.314X_1 + 0.811X_2$ means that the constant value of 2.255 is the value of employee productivity before being influenced by work safety and health.

Obaikan, Benayan, Hisham, Bassim, Yagoub (2020) examined incident reporting and its impact on quality health care service in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. This study aimed to assess the PHC provider's awareness and attitude in addition to identify the barriers of reporting the incidents. Methods: This observational cross-sectional study conducted between February 2013 and November 2014 at (Al Wazarat HC) Primary Health Center in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC). A sample size of 400 participants was selected using Stratified random sampling technique. This study shows majority of participants (91%) were aware of the meaning of the incident in health care but only 37.1% had correct knowledge of the definition.

2.3.2 Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities

Jonathan and Mbogo (2016) sought to establish teachers' perspectives on their role in ensuring health and safety workplaces in secondary schools. The study targeted all teachers and deputy principals working under Teachers Service Commission (TSC) and those working under the secondary schools' Board of Management (BOM). Although the study aimed survey principles, they were not available during the data collection period. The study was conducted using the descriptive research design. A questionnaire guide was used for data collection which was then analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20. Frequency tables and charts were used for data presentation. From the findings, it emerged that majority of the teaching staff were not involved in the training programs that would equip them with safety skills in their workplace.

Hewitt, Chreim and Forster (2016) conducted a comparative case study of two hospital divisions' use of an incident reporting system, and consider the different stages in the process and the factors that help shape the process. The data was comprised of 85 semi-structured interviews of health care practitioners in general internal medicine, obstetrics and neonatology; thematic analysis of the transcribed interviews was undertaken. Inductive and deductive themes are reported. This work is part of a larger qualitative study found elsewhere in the literature. The findings showed that there were major differences between the two divisions in terms of: a) what comprised a typical report (outcome based vs communication and near-miss based); b) how the reports were investigated (individual manager vs interdisciplinary team).

Mwangi and Waiganjo (2017) investigated the influence of occupational safety and health on employees' performance in Flower Industry in Kenya; A Case Study of Penta Flowers Limited in Thika Sub-county. The specific objectives included; to investigate the influence of OSHA training and employees' attitudes towards OSHA on employees' performance in Penta Flowers Limited, Thika Sub-county, Kiambu County, Kenya. The study adopted mixed methods approach and applied explanatory sequential design. The target population comprised of 20 management officers, 50 supervisors and 130 general workers all totaling to 200. Questionnaires were used to collect data from supervisors whereas interviews were used to collect data from management officers and general workers.

Adhika, Rihayana and Salain (2020) examined the effect of work safety and work health (OHS) on performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable on employees' performance with the contract status of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Fire and Rescue Office of Badung Selatan. The samples in this study were contract employees in the technical unit of the South Badung Fire and Rescue Service as many as 63 respondents. The analytical tool used is path analysis (path analysis). The results of the analysis explain that the variable of work safety and work health has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, in addition to directly affecting this variable also influenced by job satisfaction as an intervening variable which can be explained that job satisfaction as an intervening variable that links the variables of work safety and work health has a significant positive result on employee performance partially.

Ullah, Mohammed, Syed, Navid, Miklas and Heesup (2021) examined the role of work safety in improving social sustainability in public sector hospitals. To this effect, the researchers collected data from 431 healthcare professionals of a large public sector tertiary and teaching hospital in the city of Lahore Pakistan and analyzed the data using structural equation modeling (SEM). The results uncovered certain important facts, which were not expected per se. Job design, coworkers' behavior towards work safety, and supervisors' role in ensuring work safety are the key factors that influence social sustainability.

2.4 Gap in Knowledge

Following the review of the various empirical studies related to the objectives of the current study, the gap that this study intends to fill would be enumerated based on the objective of the study, content scope of the study, method of analysis and the geographical scope of the study. With regards to the objective of the study, the current study has a wide range of objective covering various aspects of employee health and safety as well as organizational performance, as opposed to some empirical studies reviewed which only analysed one objective. Also, the current study was on employee health and safety and performance of Local Government Councils in Enugu State while in the empirical studies reviewed, none of the empirical studies examined reviewed how employee health and safety impacted in local government councils. Furthermore, the method of analysis employed here was the Pearson Correlation analysis to capture the relationship between the two variables and their various components.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted cross-sectional descriptive survey research design. The survey design was adopted because the researcher had no control over variables of the study. It was also economical.

3.2 Area of Study

The study was conducted in Enugu East Senatorial District in Enugu State of Nigeria which covers six local government areas of Enugu East, Enugu North, Enugu South, Isi Uzo, Nkanu East and Nkanu West. Enugu East Senatorial District local government areas of Enugu State, to represent other seventeen (17) local government areas. This was because of their large population.

3.3 Sources of Data

The data used in this study was sourced from primary and secondary sources:-

Primary Data

i. **Questionnaire:** - Data were obtained from information supplied by the respondents to questions contained in the questionnaire distributed to them and the questions are framed in the most simple and unambiguous ways to enable respondents answer those questions accurately.

ii. **Secondary Data:**

A lot of materials were used, especially for the theoretical frame work of the study which is obtained from textbooks, journals, magazines newspapers and internet materials

3.4 Population of the Study

The total population of the study was one thousand three hundred and six (1306) made up 6 selected local government areas in the state – Enugu East, Enugu North, Enugu South, Isi Uzo, Nkanu East and Nkanu West local government areas of Enugu State, to represent other seventeen (17) local government areas. This was because of their large population. The study population in each of the local governments included the entire members of the local government staff and executives in the table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Population Distribution to the LGAs under study

<u>S/N</u>	<u>LOCAL AREAS</u>	<u>GOVT</u>	<u>No of the Executives</u>	<u>Local staff</u>	<u>Govt</u>	<u>Total</u>
1	Nkanu east		10	288		298
2	Enugu south		10	275		285
3	Isi Uzo		11	155		166
4	Enugu North		12	265		277
5	Nkanu west		11	145		156
6	Enugu East		11	113		124
	Total		65	1241		1306

Source: Local government offices and the communities 2022

3.5 Sample size determination

The actual population was one thousand three hundred and six (1306) staff and executives who were capable of knowing the effect of Employee Health and Safety Services and Performance of Local Government Councils in Enugu State using a simple sampling method. To determine the adequate sample size, the researcher used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu 2011).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^2 + Z^2(pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size

N = The population

p = Probability of success/proportion

q = Probability of failure/proportion

Z = Standard error of the mean

e = Limit of tolerable error (or level of significance)

N = 1306

$$p = .5$$

$$q = (1 - .5) = .5$$

$$Z = 95 \text{ percent} = 1.96$$

$$e = 0.05 \text{ percent}$$

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 1306 \times .5 \times .5}{1306(0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times .5}$$

$$\frac{3.8416 \times 1306 \times .25}{3.265 + 3.8416 \times .25}$$

$$= \frac{1254.28}{4.225} = 296.87 \approx \underline{\underline{297}}$$

3.6 Sampling Technique

Bowley’s proportional allocation formula was used to allocate the sample size to the selected states and cities. It enhanced the distribution of questionnaire to the states cities. Bowley’s proportional allocation formula is stated thus:

$$nh = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

n = The total sample size

nh = proportional sample size

Nh = population of each stratum

N = The total population under study

	Organisations	Population	Calculation	Sample
1.	Enugu North	277	$\frac{277 \times 297}{1306} =$	62
2.	Enugu south	285	$\frac{285 \times 297}{1306} =$	65
3.	Enugu East	124	$\frac{124 \times 297}{1306}$	28
4.	Isi -Uzo	166	$\frac{166 \times 297}{1306} =$	38
5.	Nkanu East	298	$\frac{298 \times 297}{1306} =$	68
6.	Nkanu west	156	$\frac{156 \times 297}{1306} =$	35
Total		1182		297

3.6 Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The questionnaire items were structured using likert 5 points scale.

3.7 Validity of Measuring Instrument

The study used five residents of each of local government under study on whom questionnaire were administered for scoring. Resource persons in the communities including my supervisor also helped in the validation of the instrument. After the scoring by each respondent, the study evaluated each respondent scoring with his own simultaneously. The results obtained from the pilot group guided the study in restructuring the instrument.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

A test-re-test method of reliability was adopted for this study in which 20 copies of 15 items questionnaire were distributed to other local government areas outside the study; five copies to each of three(3) local governments. The instrument was test using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient testing tool (Refer to table 3.3a & 3.3b). The reliability result indicated 0.811, implying a high degree of items consistency.

Table 3.3a Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test

		N	%
Cases	Valid	15	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	To tal	15	100.0

Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 3.3b Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.811	.811	15

Source: SPSS 20.0 Output

3.9. Method of Data Analyses

Data was presented in tables, percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analysing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA)-5, Agree (A)4; Neutral(N) -3; Disagree (D) - 2;Strongly Disagree(SD) 1

Decision Rule

If Mean \geq 3.0, the respondents agree

If mean \leq 3.0, the respondents disagree

Pearson correlation (r) was used to test the hypotheses, determine the nature, and strength of the research variables.

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

In this chapter, data relating to the study were presented, analyzed and interpreted. However, this section commenced with the background information of the respondents.

Table 4.1 Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

L.G.As used	Distributed	No Returned	percent	No not Returned	Percent
Enugu North	62	50	17	12	4
Enugu south	65	51	17	4	4
Enugu East	28	26	9	2	1
Isi-Uzo	38	32	11	6	2
Nkanu East	68	31	11	37	12
Nkanu West	35	20	7	15	5
Total	297	210	70	87	30

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 shows that the study distributed 297 copies of the questionnaire, two hundred and ten (210) representing (70 percent) were returned and used while 87(30 percent) were not returned and were not used.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 The relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Area Councils of Enugu State.

Table 4.2.1.1 Responses to research question one on the relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Area Councils of Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	Σ FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		
1	The provision of training on safety improves the standard of service	600 120 57.1	120 30 14.3	72 24 11.4	16 8 3.8	28 28 13.3	836 210 100%	3.98	1.431	Agree
2	Employee with skills enhances responsiveness to meet the needs of the of rates collections	575 115 54.8	108 27 12.9	78 26 12.4	28 14 6.7	28 28 13.3	817 210 100%	3.89	1.462	Agree
3	The employee ability in the local government increases the reliability of the people in their local councils	350 70 33.3	344 86 41.0	51 17 8.1	24 12 5.7	25 25 11.9	794 210 100%	3.78	1.294	Agree
4	The employee training in the local government promotes assurance of service in tax collections	505 101 48.1	160 40 19.0	81 27 12.9	36 18 8.6	24 24 11.4	806 210 100%	3.84	1.401	Agree
5	The effective record keeping as a result of skilled employees leads to the achievement of internal local government success	255 51 24.3	444 111 52.9	45 15 7.1	14 7 3.3	26 26 12.4	784 210 100%	3.73	1.224	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.844	1.3624	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.1.1, 150 respondents out of 210 representing 71.4 the provision of training on safety improves the standard of service with mean score 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.431. Employee with skills enhances responsiveness to meet the needs of the of rates collections 142 respondents representing 67.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.89 and standard deviation of 1.462. The employee ability in the local government increases the reliability of the people in their local councils 156 respondents representing 74.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.294. The staff training in the local government promotes assurance of service

141 respondents representing 67.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.84 and 1.401. The effective record keeping leads to the achievement of internal local government success 162 respondents representing 77.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.73 and standard deviation of 1.224.

4.2.2 The relationship between employee Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Area Councils of Enugu State.

Table 4.2.2.1 Responses to research question one on the relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Area Councils of Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		
1	The employees are conscious of any changes in their environment and provides medical facilities	345 69 32.9	380 95 45.2	48 16 7.6	12 6 2.9	24 24 11.4	809 210 100%	3.85	1.238	Agree
2	There is double-checking to ascertain that equipment is functioning properly	275 55 26.2	416 104 49.5	36 12 5.7	30 15 7.1	24 24 11.4	781 210 100%	3.72	1.250	Agree
3	The employees tries to recognize what could caused an accident and prevent that situation from happening in the future	315 63 30.0	304 76 36.2	78 26 12.4	34 17 8.1	28 28 13.3	759 210 100%	3.61	1.344	Agree
4	There is identification of issues in structure and function on and amenities for the staff.	250 50 23.8	428 107 51.0	15 5 2.4	30 15 7.1	33 33 15.7	756 210 100%	3.60	1.346	Agree
5	Inspecting of non-compliance with the rules and regulation are death with.	230 46 21.9	404 101 48.1	27 9 4.3	30 15 7.1	39 39 18.6	730 210 100%	3.48	1.398	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.652	1.3152	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.2.1, 164 respondents out of 210 representing 78.1 the employees are conscious of any changes in their environment and provides medical facilities with mean score 3.91 and standard deviation of 1.238. There is double-checking to ascertain that equipment is functioning properly 159 respondents representing 75.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation of 1.250. The employees tries to recognize what could caused an accident and prevent that situation from happening in the future 139 respondents representing 66.2

percent agreed with mean score of 3.61 and standard deviation of 1.344. There is identification of issues in structure and function on and amenities for the staff 157 respondents representing 74.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.60 and 1.346. Inspecting of non-compliance with the rules and regulation are death with 147 respondents representing 70.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.398.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypotheses One: There is no significant positive relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

Table 4.3.1.1: Responses on the relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

Table 4.3.1.1 Contingency table of Physical security and the academic reputation of the National open university of Nigeria.

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	The provision of training on safety improves the standard of service	120	30	24	8	28
2	Employee with skills enhances responsiveness to meet the needs of the of rates collections	115	27	26	14	28
3	The employee ability in the local government increases the reliability of the people in their local councils	70	86	17	12	25
4	The employee training in the local government promotes assurance of service in tax collections	101	40	27	18	24
5	The effective record keeping as a result of skilled employees leads to the achievement of internal local government success	51	111	15	7	26

Table 4.3.1.2 Pearson Correlation Contingency table of Physical security and the academic reputation of the National open university of Nigeria

Correlations

	The provision of training on safety improves the standard of service	Employee with skills enhances responsiveness to meet the needs of the of rates collections	The employee ability in the local government increases the reliability of the people in their local councils	The employee training in the local government promotes assurance of service in tax collections	The effective record keeping as a result of skilled employees leads to the achievement of internal local government success
The provision of training on safety improves the standard of service Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .000 210	.862** .000 210	.739** .000 210	.686** .000 210	.778** .000 210
Employee with skills enhances responsiveness to meet the needs of the of rates collections Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.862** .000 210	1 .000 210	.736** .000 210	.727** .000 210	.773** .000 210
The employee ability in the local government increases the reliability of the people in their local councils Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.739** .000 210	.736** .000 210	1 .000 210	.759** .000 210	.703** .000 210
The employee training in the local government promotes assurance of service in tax collections Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.686** .000 210	.727** .000 210	.759** .000 210	1 .000 210	.742** .000 210
The effective record keeping as a result of skilled employees leads to the achievement of internal local government success Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.778** .000 210	.773** .000 210	.703** .000 210	.742** .000 210	1 .000 210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .686 <.862. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was significant positive relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State, (r= .686 <.862). The computed

correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .686 < .862$, $p < .05$).

4.3.2 Hypotheses Two: There is no significant positive relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

Table 4.3.2.1 shows significant relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

Table 4.3.2.2 Contingency table of Physical security and the academic reputation of the National open university of Nigeria.

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	The employees are conscious of any changes in their environment and provides medical facilities	69	95	16	6	24
2	There is double-checking to ascertain that equipment is functioning properly	55	104	12	15	24
3	The employees tries to recognize what could caused an accident and prevent that situation from happening in the future	63	76	26	17	28
4	There is identification of issues in structure and function on and amenities for the staff.	50	107	5	15	33
5	Inspecting of non-compliance with the rules and regulation are death with.	46	101	9	15	39

Table 4.3.2.2 Pearson Correlation of Physical security and the academic reputation of the National open university of Nigeria.

	The employees are conscious of any changes in their environment and provides medical facilities	There is double-checking to ascertain that equipment is functioning properly	The employees tries to recognize what could caused an accident and prevent that situation from happening in the future	There is identification of issues in structure and amenities for the staff.	Inspecting of non-compliance with the rules and regulation are death with.
The employees are conscious of any changes in their environment and provides medical facilities	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.811** .000 210	.638** .000 210	.746** .000 210	.724** .000 210
There is double-checking to ascertain that equipment is functioning properly	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .000 210	.718** .000 210	.724** .000 210	.781** .000 210
The employees tries to recognize what could caused an accident and prevent that situation from happening in the future	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.638** .000 210	1 .000 210	.835** .000 210	.709** .000 210
There is identification of issues in structure and amenities for the staff.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.746** .000 210	.724** .000 210	1 .000 210	.822** .000 210
Inspecting of non-compliance with the rules and regulation are death with.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.724** .000 210	.781** .000 210	.709** .000 210	1 .000 210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.2.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.638 < .835$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that **there was significant positive relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State**, ($r = .638 < .835$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .638 < .835, p < .05$).

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 The relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State.

From the result of hypotheses one, the computed ($r = .686 < .862$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, concluded that **there was significant positive relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State** as reported in the probability value of ($r = .686 < .862, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature, Kaynack, Toklu, Elci and Toklu (2016) investigated occupational health and safety (OHS) practices in five dimensions, i.e. safety procedures and risk management, safety and health rules, first aid support and training, occupational accident prevention, and organizational safety support. The findings of the analysis suggested that such OHS practices as safety procedures and risk management, safety and health rules, first aid support and training, and organizational safety support had a positive effect on organizational commitment.

4.4.2 The relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas in Enugu State.

From the result of hypotheses two, the computed ($r = .638 < .835$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, it was concluded that **there was significant positive relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State**, as reported in the probability value of ($r = .638 < .835, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature, Jonathan and Mbogo (2016) sought to establish teachers' perspectives on their role in ensuring health and safety workplaces in secondary schools. From the findings, it emerged that majority of the teaching staff were not involved in the training programs that would equip them with safety skills in their workplace. Most of them were not involved in discussing safety policies in the workplace. This to a large extent jeopardized the safety of teachers at workplace affecting their preparedness on matters pertaining health hazards and thus their general performance.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION AND CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

5.1 Summary of Findings

i. **There was significant positive relationship between Worker Competency and training and Collection of various rates and taxes in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State**, ($r = .686 < .862, p < .05$).

ii. **There was significant positive relationship between Hazard identification and risk assessment and Provisions of health facilities in Local Government Council Areas of Enugu State**, ($r = .638 < .835, p < .05$).

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Worker Competency and training, Hazard identification and risk assessment had significant positive relationship with Collection of various rates and taxes, Provisions of health facilities of the Local Government Council Areas of Enugu state, Nigeria. A safe work environment makes workers healthy and productive. Health and safety measures are positively correlated with the performance of its employees. If there is reduced level and severity of work accidents, illness and matters related to stress, as well as improve the quality of work life of its work, there will be more effectiveness.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. There should be effective training by engaging the workers in planning process to communities in the local government and encourage the people to participate in hazard identification processes.
- ii. The staff of the local government should be mandated to do Hazard identification and risk assessment to increase risk management awareness among the staff and the people within the local government areas and also design packaged or combined policies that will cover a broad spectrum of losses that is suffered by the people.

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